

Cosmology & Multi-Messenger Astrophysics with next-gen GRB missions

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Shedding light on the early Universe with GRBs

- ❑ **Long GRBs:** huge luminosities, mostly emitted in the X and gamma-rays
- ❑ **Redshift distribution** extending at least to $z \sim 9$ and association with exploding massive stars
- ❑ **Powerful tools for cosmology:** SFR evolution, physics of re-ionization, high- z low luminosity galaxies, pop III stars

Shedding light on the early Universe with GRBs

A statistical sample of high- z GRBs can provide fundamental information:

- measure independently the **cosmic star-formation rate**, even beyond the limits of current and future galaxy surveys
- directly (or indirectly) detect the **first population of stars (pop III)**

- **Detecting and studying primordial invisible galaxies**

Robertson&Ellis12

Even **JWST** and **ELTs** surveys will be not able to probe the faint end of the galaxy Luminosity Function at high redshifts ($z > 6-8$)

• Detecting and studying primordial invisible galaxies

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- neutral hydrogen fraction
- escape fraction of UV photons from high-z galaxies
- early metallicity of the ISM and IGM and its evolution

Short GRBs and multi-messenger astrophysics

GW170817 + SHORT GRB 170817A + KN AT2017GFO (~40 Mpc):
the birth of multi-messenger astrophysics

Lightcurve from *Fermi*/GBM (50 – 300 keV)

Gravitational-wave time-frequency map

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GRB: a key phenomenon for multi-messenger astrophysics (and cosmology)

GW170817 + SHORT GRB 170817A + KN AT2017GFO
THE BIRTH OF MULTI-MESSENGER ASTROPHYSICS

Relativistic jet formation,
equation of state,
fundamental physics

Cosmic sites of r-
process nucleosynthesis

New independent route
to measure cosmological
parameters

Next generation GRB missions ('30s)

Probing the Early Universe with GRBs

Multi-messenger and time domain Astrophysics

The transient high energy sky

Synergy with next generation large facilities (E-ELT, SKA, CTA, ATHENA, GW and neutrino detectors)

- **THESEUS** (studied for ESA Cosmic Vision / M5), **HiZ-GUNDAM** (JAXA, under study), **TAP** (idea for NASA probe-class mission), **Gamow Explorer** (proposal for NASA MIDEX): **prompt emission down to soft X-rays, source location accuracy of few arcmin, prompt follow-up with NIR telescope, on-board REDSHIFT**

Future GRB missions: the case of THESEUS (ESA/M5 Phase-A study, re-proposed for M-2021)

THIS BREAKTHROUGH WILL BE ACHIEVED BY A MISSION CONCEPT
OVERCOMING MAIN LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT FACILITIES

Set of innovative wide-field monitors
with **unprecedented combination of
broad energy range from gamma-rays
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On-board **autonomous fast follow-up in
optical/NIR**, arcsec location and
redshift measurement of detected
GRB/transients

Shedding light on the early Universe with GRBs

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LIGO, Virgo, and partners make first detection of gravitational waves and light from colliding neutron stars

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THESEUS:

- ✓ short GRB detection over large FOV with arcmin localization
- ✓ Kilonova detection, arcsec localization and characterization
- ✓ Possible detection of weaker isotropic X-ray emission

THESEUS/"M7": crucial synergies in the late '30s

The «M7» timeline will allow to widely broaden the mission scientific impact by taking advantage of the perfectly matched synergies with major facilities coming fully operative in the 2030s (e.g., 3G GW detectors)

In summary

- ❖ GRBs are a key phenomenon for **cosmology** (early Universe, cosmological parameters), **multi-messenger astrophysics** and **fundamental physics**
- ❖ Next generation GRB missions, like **THESEUS**, developed by a large European collaboration and already studied by ESA (M5 Phase A) **will fully exploit these potentialities and also provide unprecedented clues to GRB physics and a substantial contribution to time-domain astronomy**
- ❖ The “M7” timeline will allow an **unprecedented great synergy with future very large observing facilities** in the e.m. and multi messenger domains, **enhancing their scientific return and fully exploiting the European leadership and investments put in them.**
- ❖ Because of the wide scope of its science goals, the great synergies and timeline and a guest-observer programme, **THESEUS scientific return will involve an unprecedented wide scientific community.**

- ❖ **THESEUS ESA/M5 Phase A study successful -> repropoed for M7 (2037)**
SPIE articles on instruments, Adv.Sp.Res. & Exp.Astr. articles on science
<http://www.isdc.unige.ch/theseus/>